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Turning climate-related information into added value for traditional **MED**iterranean **G**rape, **O**live and **D**urum wheat food systems

Deliverable 6.12

Climate Related Initiatives Interactions Report no.3

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Disclaimer

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

MED-GOLD partners have contacts with many other projects, as they are partners on those projects, or have established informal links with particular institutions. This report gives an update on work summarised in RD.1 and RD.2, which described interactions between MED-GOLD and other initiatives as part of task 6.1. This task specifically is pursuing dissemination synergies with other EU initiatives such as Climate-KIC, JPI Climate, FACE-JPI, JPI Water and related ERA-NET (e.g. ERA-NET on Climate Services) as well as clustering with other EC funded projects related to climate services via H2020 or other complementary programmes (i.e. ClimatEurope, LIFE, Copernicus, PRIMA, etc.). There is also a focus on getting involved with other initiatives related to agriculture that include a significant climate component.. This deliverable focuses on the period December 2019 to November 2020. There were no deviations from the DoA.

The main steps of the activities described in this report are as follows. MED-GOLD partners were asked to provide details of existing interactions with other projects and possible new interactions. They were also invited to summarise abstracts submitted to forthcoming conferences. The interactions and conferences are summarised in five tables.

1. OBJECTIVES

With this deliverable, the project has contributed to the achievement of the following objectives (DOA, Part B Table1.1):

No.	Objective	Yes
1	To co-design, co-develop, test, and assess the added value of proof-of-concept climate services for olive, grape, and durum wheat	
2	To refine, validate, and upscale the three pilot services with the wider European and global user communities for olive, grape, and durum wheat	
3	To ensure replicability of MED-GOLD climate services in other crops/climates (e.g., coffee) and to establish links to policy making globally	X
4	To implement a comprehensive communication and commercialization plan for MED-GOLD climate services to enhance market uptake	X
5	To build better informed and connected end-user communities for the global olive oil, wine, and pasta food systems and related policy making	X

2. IMPACT

Please describe briefly how this deliverable contributes to the relevant expected impacts of the work programme

No.	Expected impact	Yes
1	Providing added-value for the decision-making process addressed by the project, in terms of effectiveness, value creation, optimised opportunities and minimised risk	
2	Enhancing the potential for market uptake of climate services demonstrated by addressing the added value	
3	Ensuring the replicability of the methodological frameworks for value-added climate services in potential end-user markets	X
4	To implement a comprehensive communication and commercialization plan for MED-GOLD climate services to enhance market uptake	X
5	To build better informed and connected end-user communities for the global olive oil, wine, and pasta food systems and related policy making	X

3. DEFINITIONS

Concepts and terms used in this document and needing a definition are included in the following table.

Table 3-1 Definitions

Concept / Term	Definition
Climate service	The provision of climate information in such a way as to assist decision-making

4. ACRONYMS

Acronyms used in this document and needing a definition are included in the following table.

Table 4-1 Acronyms

Acronym	Definition
ADAPT2CLIMA	Adaptation to Climate Change Impacts on the Mediterranean islands' Agriculture
AfriCultuRes	Enhancing Food Security in African AgriCultural Systems with the support of Remote Sensing
AgMIP	The Agricultural Model Intercomparison and Improvement Project
Agri Adapt	Sustainable adaptation of typical EU farming systems to climate change
BeFOre	Bioresources for Oliviculture
BSC	Barcelona Supercomputing Center - Centro Nacional de Supercomputacion
CAFE	Climate Advanced Forecasting of sub-seasonal Extremes
CEEV	Comité Européen des Entreprises Vins
CLARITY	Integrated Climate Adaptation Service Tools for Improving Resilience Measure Efficiency
Climate-KIC	EIT Climate Knowledge and Innovation Community
EASME	Executive Agency for SMEs
EIT	European Institute of Innovation and Technology
ERA	European Research Area (e.g.: ERA-NET)
EUCLID	Europe China Lever for IPM Demonstration
EUSTACE	EU Surface Temperature for All Corners of Earth
FACCE-JPI	Joint Programming Initiative on Agriculture, Food Security and Climate Change
H2020	Horizon 2020
IMPRES	IMproving PRedictions and management of hydrological EXTremes
IPM	Integrated Pest Management
JPI	Joint Programming Initiative
LIFE AGRESTIC	Reduction of Agricultural GReenhouse gases EmiSsions Through Innovative Cropping systems
MACSUR	Modelling European Agriculture with Climate Change for Food Security
MedECC	Mediterranean Experts on Climate and environmental Change

MED-GOLD	Turning climate-related information into added value for traditional MEDiterranean Grape, Olive and Durum wheat food systems
MEDSCOPE	MEDiterranean Services Chain based On climate PrEdictions
NDVI	Normalized Difference Vegetation Index
NEREUS	Network of European Regions Using Space Technologies
OLIVE4CLIMATE	Climate Change Mitigation Through a Sustainable Supply Chain for the Olive Oil Sector
OLIVE-MIRACLE	Modelling solutions for improved and Resilient mAnagement strategies for Olive tree against future CLimatE change
PEFMED	Uptake of the Product Environmental Footprint across the MED agrofood regional productive systems to enhance innovation and market value
PRIMA	Partnership for Research and Innovation in the Mediterranean Area
PRIMAVERA	Process-based climate sIMulation: AdVances in high-resolution modelling and European climate Risk Assessment.
PROSNOW	Provision of a prediction system allowing for management and optimization of snow in Alpine ski resorts
PUCS	Pan-European Urban Climate Services
PURE	Pesticide Use-and-risk Reduction in European farming systems with Integrated Pest Management
S2S4E	Sub-seasonal to Seasonal climate forecasting for Energy
SECLI-FIRM	The Added Value of Seasonal Climate Forecasts for Integrated Risk Management Decisions
SoIACE	Solutions for improving Agroecosystem and Crop Efficiency for water and nutrient use
VISCA	Vineyards Integrated Smart Climate Application

5. REFERENCES

The following documents, although not part of this document, amplify or clarify its contents. Reference documents are those not applicable and referenced within this document. They are referenced in this document in the form [RD.x]:

Table 5-1 References

Ref.	Title	Code	Version	Date
[RD.1]	Climate Related Initiatives Interactions Report no.1	D6.1	2.0	01-12-2018
[RD.2]	Climate Related Initiatives Interactions Report no.2	D6.11	1.5	01-12-2019
[RD.3]				

6. DETAILED REPORT

6.1. STATE OF THE ART

A wide range of innovative projects on climate services and agriculture are underway, including MED-GOLD. Many partners on MED-GOLD coordinate or are participants in some of these projects, and have established formal and informal links with other projects. These links allow ideas from MED-GOLD to be promoted, and new results from other projects to be incorporated into MED-GOLD.

6.2 METHODS

MED-GOLD project partners were approached and asked to summarise projects related to climate services and agriculture that they are involved with, either as coordinators or partners. They were also requested to describe other initiatives that could be of interest to MED-GOLD, or those that might benefit from links with MED-GOLD. Finally, partners provided titles of presentations given at conferences and workshops where MED-GOLD was promoted, or results were discussed.

6.3 MAIN RESULTS

The interactions with various initiatives are divided into three main groups: climate services, agriculture, and conferences. Those related to climate services and agriculture are split into two further groups: initiatives in which MED-GOLD partners are currently involved, either as coordinators or partners (Tables 6-1 and 6-2), and those where interactions could be beneficial to MED-GOLD, but no formal links have yet been established (Tables 6-3 and 6-4). In some cases, the links are via social media such as Twitter feeds. For the period considered in this report (December 2019 to November 2020), MED-GOLD partners are involved in thirteen projects related to climate services and an additional thirteen on agriculture.

Table 6-5 summarises fifteen conferences and workshops where MED-GOLD results could be promoted, and where results from other projects could be of interest. MED-GOLD partners gave presentations at (or are due to present at) eight of these events. Three events have been postponed owing to the Covid-19 pandemic, and will take place in December 2020 or later in 2021. One event (43rd World Congress of Vine and Wine) has been cancelled, but is included for completeness.

6.3.1 DESCRIPTION OF INITIATIVES RELATED TO CLIMATE SERVICES THAT MED-GOLD IS WORKING WITH

MED-GOLD partners are either coordinators or partners in many other projects whose aim is to develop climate services, as summarised in Table 6-1. For example, the Met Office led PRIMAVERA and ClimatEurope. BSC are partners on Indecis and MEDSCOPE and coordinate S2S4E. Other interactions occurred where MED-GOLD partners were invited to international meetings on climate services, and experts from other projects gave presentations at events organised by MED-GOLD (e.g., the Living Lab). A total of 13 initiatives are summarised in Table 6-1.

Table 6-1 Description of initiatives related to climate services that MED-GOLD is working with.

Initiative	Type	Description	Status	Interaction	MED-GOLD Contact
CLARA	H2020	Stakeholder engagements: agricultural case study community; new techniques for assessing the added value of climate services to be applied in MED-GOLD. http://www.clara-project.eu/	Ongoing	CLARA presented by Francesca Larosa at MED-GOLD GA in Sardinia October 2019.	Met Office (via ClimatEurope)
ClimatEurope	H2020	Coordination and support action that pursues synergies with other EU initiatives through a Europe-wide network for researchers, suppliers and users of climate information. https://www.climateurope.eu ClimatEurope is due to end in November 2020.	Ongoing	Participation includes a round table discussion on the future of wine, an interactive session discussing user needs and solutions and two posters, one introducing MED-GOLD project and another describing communication, engagement and clustering activities. A section with a general description of MED-GOLD available on the ClimatEurope website.	Met Office, BSC, SOGRAPE
Climate-KIC (Knowledge and Innovation Community)		Climate-KIC is a European knowledge and innovation community, working to accelerate the transition to a zero-carbon economy. Supported by the European Institute of Innovation and Technology (EIT). http://www.climate-kic.org/	Ongoing	Some informal contacts.	ENEA, Univ Leeds

Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S)		<p>http://www.copernicus.eu/</p> <p>Includes a global agriculture project that may be of interest/use.</p> <p>https://climate.copernicus.eu/global-agriculture-project</p>	Ongoing	<p>The director of C3S is a member of the external advisory committee of MED-GOLD (participated in the second annual GA in Cagliari, October 2019).</p> <p>ENEA and Beetobit visited C3S (Reading) to discuss criticalities in the use of Climate Data Store.</p> <p>An expert from C3S gave a keynote talk at the MED-GOLD Living Lab.</p> <p>Met Office are also partners in C3S.</p>	ENEA, Met Office, Beetobit
EC Directorate-General for Climate Action (DG CLIMA)		Institution that leads the European Commission's efforts to fight climate change at EU and international level.	Ongoing	Policy officer of DG CLIMA invited BSC to attend a general discussion about the work done in different climate services related projects (MED-GOLD among them).	BSC
European Geosciences Union (EGU)		<p>The European Geosciences Union (EGU) is the leading organisation for Earth, planetary and space science research in Europe.</p> <p>https://www.egu.eu/</p>	Ongoing	Submitted proposal for endorsement and financial support of the MED-GOLD summer school in Cagliari (May 2020). No support granted, but the event was replaced by the Living Lab (online only).	ENEA
Indecis	ERA4CS / ERA-NET / JPI	<p>Indecis is concerned with the development across Europe of user-oriented climate indicators for GFCS high-priority sectors: agriculture, disaster risk reduction, energy, health, water and tourism.</p> <p>http://www.indecis.eu/</p>	Ongoing	BSC are partners on Indecis.	BSC

MEDSCOPE	ERA4CS	MEDSCOPE is working on optimisation of seasonal forecasts of Mediterranean region, this is possibly of interest for MED-GOLD. https://www.medscope-project.eu/	Ongoing	BSC are partners on MEDSCOPE.	BSC
PRIMAVERA	H2020	PRIMAVERA aims to develop a new generation of advanced and well-evaluated high-resolution global climate models, capable of simulating and predicting regional climate with unprecedented fidelity, for the benefit of governments, business and society in general. https://www.primavera-h2020.eu/	Completed	The Met Office coordinated the PRIMAVERA project. Primavera high-resolution data outputs (particularly 'stream2' even higher resolution) could be of use for MED-GOLD. Several factsheets were created on various topics including aspects of climate modelling and climate impacts. PRIMAVERA ended in July 2020.	Met Office, BSC
S2S4E (Sub-seasonal to Seasonal climate forecasting for Energy)	H2020	S2S4E will offer an innovative service to improve renewable energy (RE) variability management by developing new research methods exploring the frontiers of weather conditions for future weeks and months. https://s2s4e.eu/	Ongoing	Developing case studies for different energy related sectors as well as a visualization platform with sub-seasonal and seasonal climate predictions that can provide some ideas to MED-GOLD.	BSC (coordinators), ENEA
SECLI-FIRM The added value of Seasonal Climate Forecasts for Integrated Risk Management Decisions)	H2020	The central objective of SECLI-FIRM is to demonstrate how the use of improved climate forecasts, out to several months ahead, can add practical and economic value to decision-making processes and outcomes, primarily in the energy sector, but also in the water sector. http://www.secli-firm.eu/	Ongoing	Met Office and ENEA are partners on this project.	Met Office

UfM Union for the Mediterranean		Intergovernmental institution bringing together the 28 European Union Member States and 15 countries from the Southern and Eastern shores of the Mediterranean to promote dialogue and cooperation. https://ufmsecretariat.org	Ongoing	UfM invited BSC to give a presentation on climate innovation and how climate services can help societies to adapt to climate variability and change. https://ufmsecretariat.org/ufm-climate-week-2019/	BSC
VISCA	H2020	VISCA is a project providing a climate service and decision support system integrating climate. Agricultural and end-user requirements to design medium to long-term adaptation strategies to climate change. http://visca.eu/ VISCA will end in December 2020.	Ongoing	VISCA are producing a seasonal forecast for Wine case study, possibly of interest for MED-GOLD.	BSC

6.3.2 DESCRIPTION OF AGRICULTURAL INITIATIVES THAT MED-GOLD IS WORKING WITH

Many of the interactions summarised in Table 6-2 are less formal than those in Table 6-1. For example, BSC and Sogrape participated in a scoping workshop organised by CLIMALERT. BSC provided feedback on the Farm to Fork strategy. HORTA are one of the coordinators of a new project, LIFE AGRESTIC, which started in October 2020. A total of 13 initiatives are summarised in Table 6-2.

Table 6-2 Description of initiatives related to agriculture with which MED-GOLD is working.

Initiative	Type	Description	Status	Interaction	MED-GOLD Contact
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ADAPT2CLIMA	LIFE	<p>The main aim of LIFE ADAPT2CLIMA project is to increase knowledge on the vulnerability of EU Mediterranean agriculture to climate change and to support decision making for adaptation planning. The methodology is based on the deployment of a set of climate, hydrological and crop simulation models for the assessment of climate change impacts on agriculture, as well as, on the development of a decision support tool for the elaboration of adaptation strategies for the agricultural sector.</p> <p>http://adapt2clima.eu</p>	Ongoing	The climatic indices developed for olive trees in the Mediterranean in the framework of ADAPT2CLIMA were discussed in the WP2 workshop of MED-GOLD and formed the basis of climate indices adopted in the framework of the respective work package (WP2).	NOA
BeFOre		<p>This projects' aim is to establish a multilateral network of research and innovation staff active in OLIVE germplasm access, conservation, evaluation and exploitation. Strengthening research capacities through the exchange of knowledge and expertise on a shared research programme focused on establishing integrated common protocols to phenotype and characterize plants at molecular, morphological and physiological level, and evaluating the olive oil quality related to varieties.</p> <p>http://www.beforeproject.eu/</p>	Ongoing	None so far but they welcome future interaction.	ENEA
CEEV (Comité Européen des Entreprises Vins)		<p>Representative body of the EU Industry and trade in wines.</p> <p>https://www.ceev.eu/</p>	Ongoing	The Secretary General of strategic orientation, representation, press relations and daily management gave an invited talk during the MED-GOLD General Assembly 2019.	ENEA, SOGRAPE

CLIMALERT ERA4CS	JPI	<p>Part of JPI Climate - this is a Climate Alert Smart System for Sustainable Water and Agriculture.</p> <p>http://www.jpi-climate.eu/nl/25223440-CLIMALERT.html</p> <p>http://climalert.eu/</p>	Ongoing	<p>BSC and SOGRAPE participated in the Scoping Workshop "Future research needs in support of Climate Services":</p> <p>Francisco Doblas-Reyes chaired the general discussion in session 2 « What have we done in JPI Climate and what do we want to do next? Introductory presentations»</p> <p>Asun St. Clair presented «The Mission Adaptation»</p> <p>António Graça presented « Main hurdles delaying adoption of CS by the European grape and wine sector».</p>	BSC, SOGRAPE
COPA-COGECA		<p>Lobby organization representing agricultural cooperatives. They are participating in the design and development of public European policies.</p> <p>https://copa-cogeca.eu</p>	Ongoing	<p>Prof. Anna Rufolo is a member of the external advisory committee of MED-GOLD.</p> <p>Policy advisors for the wine and olive sector participated to interview to discuss how MED-GOLD results could be useful for the policy community.</p>	BSC, ENEA
DOUROZONE		<p>Supported by the Portuguese National Foundation for Science and Technology. This project aims to evaluate the risk of ozone exposure for vineyards of Douro Wine Region under present and future climate scenarios. There are potential bidirectional interactions with MED-GOLD.</p> <p>They have developed an Atlas:</p> <p>http://dao-dourozone.ua.pt/atlas/</p>	Ongoing	<p>They have agreed to give access to their data for use in MED-GOLD. Specifically, they have simulations for Iberian Peninsula for the periods 1986-2005, 2046-2065, 2081-2100 using RCP8.5 scenario with a grid of 9 km.</p> <p>After that, they selected a few years and a 1 km dynamical downscaling (WRF) for the Douro Wine Region made for forcing an air quality model.</p>	SOGRAPE
Evoinos (The Heritage Project, Cyprus Wine Project)		<p>Evoinos strives for knowledge and capacity building through advocacy, cultural management to engage and inspire diverse professional and non-professional wine loving audiences.</p> <p>https://evoinos.com/</p>	Ongoing	<p>The Twitter accounts @evoinos and MED-GOLD follow each other.</p> <p>This project also has Instagram and Facebook presence through which we can connect.</p> <p>Info@evoinos.com</p>	Through social media

Farm to Fork Strategy	EC	Feedback was sought by the EC on the farm-to-fork strategy. It sets out the regulatory and non-regulatory measures needed to create more efficient, climate-smart systems that provide healthy food, while securing a decent living for EU farmers and fishermen.	Finished	The importance of considering the role of climate services was raised in feedback from MED-GOLD. Feedback reference: F508222.	BSC
IMPRESX (IMproving PRedictions and management of hydrological Extremes)	H2020	This project aims to enhance forecast quality of extreme hydro-meteorological conditions and their impacts. MED-GOLD is interested in any agriculture and drought case studies they might produce. http://impresx.eu/	Completed	Many datasets created for specific river basins, but none coincides with MED-GOLD study regions. IMPRESX ended in December 2019.	BSC
LIFE AGRESTIC (Reduction of Agricultural Greenhouse gases Emissions Through Innovative Cropping systems)	LIFE	This project aims to promote the adoption of innovative and efficient cropping systems, based on the introduction of legumes and catch crops in four-year rotations of cereals and industrial crops, and of innovative tools in order to mitigate the impact of agricultural activity on climate change and optimize agronomic management.	Ongoing	HORTA is one of the coordinators of this project.	HORTA
MAPA (Ministerio de Agricultura, Pesca y Alimentación)		Department of the Government of Spain responsible for proposing and carrying out the government policy on agricultural, livestock and fishery resources, food industry, rural development and human food.	Ongoing	Representatives from the division on herbaceous cultures and olive oil participated in interviews to discuss how MED-GOLD results could be useful for the policy community.	BSC
PRIMA (Partnership for Research and Innovation in the Mediterranean Area)	H2020	A joint programme focused on the development and application of solutions for food systems and water resources in the Mediterranean basin. http://ec.europa.eu/research/environment/index.cfm?pg=prima	Ongoing	PRIMA coordinator is a member of the MED-GOLD External Advisory Committee.	ENEA
Tierras De Mollina		Comprises 600 cooperatives, 844 ha of vineyards, producing 80% of musts and wines under the designation 'origin Malaga'. https://www.tierrasdemollina.com/	Ongoing	The Twitter accounts @VinosdeMollina and @medgold_H2020 follow each other. This might be a good option for future workshop invitations: vitivinicola@virgendelaoliva.com	Through social media

6.3.3 DESCRIPTION OF INITIATIVES RELATED TO CLIMATE SERVICES FOR POSSIBLE FUTURE INTERACTIONS

In this section, 17 other climate service initiatives that might be of interest to MED-GOLD are summarised in Table 6-3. These initiatives do not address the sectors that are the focus of MED-GOLD (i.e., olives, vines and durum wheat). MED-GOLD partners coordinate some of these initiatives (e.g., GMV coordinate AfriCultuRes, BSC are partners on FOCUS-Africa). Several of the existing interactions occur via social media.

Table 6-3 Description of other initiatives related to climate services.

Initiative	Type	Description	Status	Interaction	MED-GOLD Contact
AfriCultuRes (Enhancing Food Security in African AgriCultural Systems with the support of Remote Sensing)	H2020	To design, implement and demonstrate an integrated agricultural monitoring and early warning system that will support decision making in the field of food security. http://www.africultures.eu/	Ongoing	Preliminary conversations held. In a second meeting GMV explained the services offered by MED-GOLD. The AfriCulture coordinator was interested in some examples of replicability. PBDM applied to armyworm in Maize crops. A third meeting is on the table.	GMV (project coordinators)
APPLICATE (Advanced Prediction in Polar regions and beyond)	H2020	The aim of this project is to enhance predictive capacity for weather and climate in the Arctic and beyond. Due to end in October 2020. https://applycate.eu/	Ongoing	The Twitter accounts @APPLICATE and @medgold_H2020 follow each other.	BSC, Met Office
BLUE-ACTION (Arctic impact on weather and climate)	H2020	Project on Arctic impact on climate and weather. http://blueaction.eu/	Ongoing	The Twitter accounts @BG10Blueaction and @medgold_H2020 follow each other. Coordinator: Steffen M. Olsen DMI smo@dmi.dk	Via social media and ClimatEurope
CAFÉ (Climate Advanced Forecasting of sub-seasonal Extremes)	Marie Skłodowska-Curie Innovative Training Network	Project focused on climate extremes http://www.cafes2se-itn.eu/	Ongoing	Showing interest in collaborating with MED-GOLD.	BSC
CLARITY	H2020	CLARITY will provide an operational eco-system of	Ongoing	We follow their Twitter account @growobservatory	Met Office

(Integrated Climate Adaptation Service Tools for Improving Resilience Measure Efficiency)		cloud-based climate services to calculate and present the expected effects of CC-induced and amplified hazards at the level of risk, vulnerability and impact functions. CLARITY will offer what-if decision support functions to investigate the effects of adaptation measures and risk reduction options in the specific project context and allow the comparison of alternative strategies. http://clarity-h2020.eu/			
EO4SD	ESA	EO4SD – Earth Observation for Sustainable Development – is a new ESA initiative which aims to achieve a step increase in the uptake of satellite-based environmental information in the IFIs regional and global programs. It will follow a systematic, user-driven approach in order to meet longer-term, strategic geospatial information needs in the individual developing countries, as well as international and regional development organizations. https://eo4sd.esa.int/	Completed	EO-based information and services can support agricultural monitoring and management tasks.	GMV
EUSTACE	H2020	EUSTACE used surface skin temperature from satellites to estimate daily air temperature globally. These data are of possible interest for MED-GOLD. https://www.eustaceproject.eu/	Finished	Project was led by the Met Office.	Met Office
FOCUS-Africa (Full-value chain Optimised Climate User-centric Services for Southern Africa)	H2020	Aim: to develop sustainable tailored climate services in the Southern African Development Community to illustrate how the application of new climate forecasts, projections and resources from Copernicus, GFCS and other relevant products can maximise socio-economic benefits in the Southern Africa region and potentially in the whole of Africa. Agriculture and food security is one of the four sectors targeted.	Started September 2020	BSC are a partner in this project.	BSC
Grow Observatory	H2020	This project is addressing science challenges and data	Ongoing	None so far	None

		gaps, from creating soil maps to enhancing climate prediction models and earth observation from satellites. https://growobservatory.org/			
ISlopedia	ERA4CS/ JPI Climate	ISlopedia will be an online portal for national-level, cross-sectoral climate-impact assessments, based on state-of-the-art climate-impacts simulations from ISIMIP. ISlopedia will include a new round of ISIMIP climate-impacts simulations. The focus topic of the simulation round will be decided upon in consultation with relevant interest groups and stakeholders. Stakeholders will also contribute to designing the ISlopedia web portal, including the content of the impact assessments. https://www.isimip.org/isipedia/	Ongoing	Inga Menke inga.menke@climateanalytics.org Quentin Lejeune quentin.lejeune@climateanalytics.org The Twitter accounts @ISL_pedia and @medgold_H2020 follow each other.	Via social media
JPI Water	JPI	http://www.wateripi.eu/	Ongoing	We follow their Twitter account @WaterJPI	Via social media
JPI Climate	JPI	http://www.jpi-climate.eu/home	Ongoing	Met Office has links with JPI Climate through the H2020 project ClimatEurope.	Met Office
LANDMARK Project	H2020	LANDMARK is a European research project on the sustainable management of land and soil in Europe. The questions that the project addresses are: "How can we make the most of our land? How can we ensure that our soils deliver on the many expectations we have of our land?" http://landmark2020.eu/	Ongoing	We follow their Twitter account @Landmark2020.	Via social media.
NEREUS (Network of European Regions Using Space Technologies)		As Network of European Regions Using Space Technologies, NEREUS offers a dynamic platform to all Regions aiming at making a better use of space applications for the delivery of	None at present	Were contacted by MED-GOLD but did not respond.	ENEA

		<p>efficient public policies benefiting citizens.</p> <p>www.nereus-regions.eu</p>			
<p>PROSNOW</p> <p>(Provision of a prediction system allowing for management and optimization of snow in Alpine ski resorts)</p>		<p>The PROSNOW project ambitions to build a demonstrator of a meteorological and climate prediction system from one week to several months ahead applied to snow management, specifically tailored to the needs of the ski industry using a co-design approach. This novel climate service holds significant potential to increase the resilience of socio-economic mountain stakeholders and supports their real-time climate change adaptation potential.</p> <p>http://prosnow.org/</p>	Ongoing	<p>The Met Office has links with PROSNOW through ClimatEurope's working group on climate services projects.</p> <p>We follow their Twitter account @PROSNOW.</p>	Met Office
<p>PUCS</p> <p>Pan-European Urban Climate Services</p> <p>Also known as Climate-fit.city</p>	H2020	<p>PUCS aims at a genuine market uptake of (urban) climate services, based on a distributed network of local business intermediaries throughout Europe, enhancing the awareness for urban climate-related issues in the end-user community, and converting (mature) research results into tailored added-value information, thus removing important barriers for the deployment of urban climate services.</p> <p>http://climate-fit.city/</p>	Ongoing	<p>The Twitter accounts @Climatefit and @medgold_H2020 follow each other.</p>	Met Office

6.3.4 DESCRIPTION OF INITIATIVES RELATED TO AGRICULTURE FOR POSSIBLE FUTURE INTERACTIONS

In this section, 14 agriculture initiatives that might be of interest to MED-GOLD are summarised in Table 6-4. Attempts to establish links with these initiatives has been less successful than those in Table 6-3. In several cases, the projects were contacted by MED-GOLD partners but no response was received. The strongest links are with Cenecafe (Universidad Militar in Colombia) and VITIGEOSS, in which BSC are a partner.

Table 6-4 Description of other initiatives related to agriculture

Initiative	Type	Description	Status	Interaction	MED-GOLD Contact
AgMIP	Global UK/US government funded initiative	Major international effort linking the climate, crop, and economic modelling communities supported by the UK Department for International Development's UKaid, in partnership with the US Department of Agriculture Agricultural Research Service. http://www.agmip.org/about-us/people/	Ongoing	Prof. Bruno Basso (Michigan State University, USA) is a member of the MED-GOLD External Advisory Committee.	ENEA
Agri Adapt	LIFE	This project aims to demonstrate how sustainable adaptation measures can help livestock, arable and permanent crop farms become more climate resilient. https://agriadapt.eu/	Ongoing	None so far	None
Genecafé		A climate network for coffee growers in Colombia which is supported by Federacafe. It has online access with useful climate information for producers. They publish the "Anuario Meterológico Cafetero" compiling the annual climate information from numerous ground stations, all located in traditional coffee growing areas. They provided general information about best planting dates in different regions of Colombia and rain forecast. https://agroclima.cenicafe.org/	Ongoing	MED-GOLD partners in Colombia have interacted with various people.	Universidad Militar

Global Agriculture Sectoral Information System	Copernicus	<p>A project funded by the European Commission designed to support society by providing authoritative information about the past, present and future climate for adaptation and mitigation purposes by providing consistent and authoritative information about climate change. Their Climate Data Store offers free and open access to climate data and tools.</p> <p>http://www.copernicus.eu/</p>	Ongoing	<p>Copernicus has a global agriculture project as part of this which may be of interest/use.</p> <p>https://climate.copernicus.eu/global-agriculture-project</p>	Met Office
EUCLID		<p>The overall objective is to secure food production for the increasing worldwide population while developing sustainable production methodologies to fight pests with an Integrated Pest Management approach (IPM), to be used in European and Chinese agriculture.</p> <p>www.euclidipm.org/</p>	Ongoing	None so far	None
FACCEJPI	JPI	<p>The Joint Programming Initiative on Agriculture, Food Security and Climate Change (FACCE-JPI) brings together 24 countries who are committed to building an integrated European Research Area addressing the interconnected challenges of sustainable agriculture, food security and impacts of climate change.</p> <p>https://www.faccejpi.com/Research-Themes-and-Achievements</p>	Ongoing	None so far	None
LIFE	LIFE	<p>http://ec.europa.eu/environment/life/about/index.htm</p>	Ongoing	None so far	None

OLIVE4CLIMATE	LIFE	<p>The project will test and verify innovative approaches and demonstrative actions aimed at the implementation of climate change mitigation strategies linked to the olive oil supply chain.</p> <p>https://olive4climate.eu/en/</p>	Ongoing	None so far	None
OLIVECLIMA project		<p>Investigating the introduction of new olive crop management practices focused on climate change mitigation and adaptation.</p> <p>http://www.oliveclima.eu/en/</p>	Ongoing	None so far	None
OLIVE-MIRACLE	JPI	<p>(FACCE SURPLUS, part of the FACCE JPI program) Modelling solutions for Improved and Resilient Management strategies for Olive tree against future climate change.</p> <p>The aim of this project is to provide accurate tools to test the effectiveness of adaptation/mitigation management strategies to support long-term investment decision making on olive-tree cultivation across the Mediterranean under current and future climate.</p> <p>http://facceturplus.org/research-projects-1st-call/olive-miracle/</p>	Ongoing	<p>OLIVE-MIRACLE have been involved with the project since the proposal stage supporting the project as a stakeholder and as such has ongoing interest in MEDGOLD.</p> <p>Letter of support provided for proposal can be seen here: https://drive.google.com/file/d/0B3sKhdbcDv_jRXkzUVBVWjYxZ1k/view?usp=sharing</p>	ENECA
SolACE	H2020	<p>The goal of SolACE - Solutions for improving Agroecosystem and Crop Efficiency for water and nutrient use - is to help European agriculture face major challenges, notably increased rainfall variability and reduced use of N and P fertilizers.</p> <p>https://www.solace-eu.net/</p>	Ongoing	None so far	None

SUSTAIN OLIVE	PRIMA	The main goal of SUSTAINOLIVE is to improve the sustainability of the olive oil sector, through the implementation and promotion of a set of innovative sustainable management solutions, based on agro-ecological concepts, as well as in the exchange of knowledge and participation of multiple associates and end users. https://sustainolive.eu/?lang=en	Ongoing	Coordinators approached to join the MED-GOLD community.	DCOOP
VITIGEOSS (Vineyard Innovative Tool based on the InteGration of Earth Observation Services and in-field Sensors)	H2020	Aims to create an innovative commercial information delivery to optimize sustainable vine cultivation via decision support systems (DSS) on phenology, irrigation, fertilizer, disease and business operations management.	Started September 2020	BSC participating as partner.	BSC
WHEAT	CGIAR	WHEAT is a global alliance unparalleled in the history of wheat research. WHEAT is a CGIAR Research Program launched in 2012 and led by the International Maize and Wheat Improvement Center (CIMMYT). http://wheat.org/	Ongoing	None so far	None

6.3.5 EVENTS THAT ARE OF POSSIBLE INTEREST FOR MAKING NEW CONTACTS.

Conferences, workshops and other events where MED-GOLD could be promoted and useful contacts made are listed in Table 6-5. Some events have been either postponed or cancelled owing to the Covid-19 pandemic. MED-GOLD partners participated in eight out of fifteen events.

Table 6-5 Description of conferences and workshops of interest

Title	Date	Location	Other Info	Audience and project members attending?
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8th Conference of Agro-food cooperatives	26 - 27 March 2020	Toledo, Spain.	Postponed owing to the Covid-19 pandemic. A new date for this conference has not been confirmed.	DCOOP created a poster outlining the aims of MED-GOLD.
EGU2020	4 - 8 May 2020	Vienna, Austria (online)	https://equ2020.eu/	Two presentations were given by MED-GOLD partners (abstracts EGU2020-7046 and EGU2020-20694).
III OLEA International Project Networking Event	23 - 25 May 2020	Universidad de Jaén (online)	https://www.ujaen.es/servicios/ofipi/olea-initiative	ENEA and DCOOP gave a presentation on MED-GOLD.
ClimatEurope Webstivals	Various, summer to autumn 2020	Online	https://www.climateurope.eu/events-climateurope/festival/webstival-2020-home-page/ Kick-off event held on 18 June 2020.	Met Office coordinates ClimatEurope. Second event on 17 September "Tools, demo cases, analyses and platforms" attended by MED-GOLD partners
Smart Agrifood Summit	24 - 25 September 2020	Málaga, Spain	https://smartagrifoodsummit.com/	DCOOP gave a presentation on MED-GOLD, focusing on the ICT platform.
Salone del Gusto	From 8 October 2020	Online	https://terramadresalonedelgusto.com/en/ Event has been reorganised owing to the Covid-19 pandemic. Various online events will be held from October 2020 to April 2021.	
ClimRisk2020: Time for Action!	21 - 23 October	Online	https://www.sisclima.it/conferenza-annuale-2020/	ENEA gave a presentation on experiences with an online training event, the MED-GOLD Living Lab.
XIII International Terroir Congress	17 - 18 November 2020	Online	https://terroircongress.org.au/	Met Office and SOGRAPE gave a short presentation on unprecedented high rainfall totals over northern Portugal. SOGRAPE co-chaired session 1, "Scales of Terroir".
1st Agroecology Congress	19-21 November 2020	Extremadura, Spain	https://www.congresoagroecoextremadura.org/programa	BSC gave a talk "Hacia una agricultura más resiliente: predicciones climáticas adaptadas a las necesidades del sector" (Towards more resilient agriculture: climate predictions tailored to the needs of the sector).

43rd World Congress of Vine and Wine	23 - 27 November 2020	Santiago, Chile	http://www.oiv.int/en/ Cancelled owing to the Covid-19 pandemic. Plans underway to promote these congresses in other formats. The 44 th Congress, which was to be held in Uzbekistan in 2021, has also been cancelled.	
The Future of Wine	26 - 27 November 2020	London, UK (online)	https://sustainablewine.co.uk/	BSC gave a presentation on "Lessons from Spain: How the wine industry can tackle sustainability and climate change."
Global Food Security Conference	7 - 9 December 2020	Montpellier, France (online)	http://www.globalfoodsecurityconference.com/ Postponed from June 2020. Topic 5 - How to assess future food security: on foresight, forecasting, projecting, predicting and exploring the future - could be relevant.	
EGU2021	25 - 30 April 2021	Vienna, Austria.	https://www.egu2021.eu/	
7th International Congress of Mountain and Steep Slopes Viticulture	May 2021	Vila Real, Portugal.	https://viicongresscervim.utad.pt/index.aspx Postponed from 2020.	Researchers, consultants, technical staff, farmers.
International Cool Climate Wine Symposium	25 - 29 July 2021	Brock University, Ontario, Canada	http://iccws2020.ca/ Postponed from 2020.	Scientists, consultants, policy-makers, entrepreneurs, technicians, students.

7. EXPLOITATION OF RESULTS

Since RD.1 and RD.2 were submitted, the information contained within these tables has been updated using shared documents within the MED-GOLD consortium. Connections have been made with many other initiatives via many channels. Some MED-GOLD partners also coordinate or are partners in these initiatives. Other connections have been established by giving oral presentations and posters at conferences, and communication via social media channels, mostly Twitter. For some projects and initiatives, these connections are sufficient (for instance, where relevance is vague or tangential to the aims of MED-GOLD). The process of updating these tables is ongoing, and this deliverable is due to be updated again in May 2021. Moving forward, as more projects and initiatives come to an end, these tables will be divided to record past projects separately. In addition to initiatives and projects, relevant conferences and workshops that could be pertinent to the MED-GOLD project are summarised, together with details of which MED-GOLD partner attended and their roles (e.g., giving an oral presentation, chairing a session). As more consortium members attend such events, more potential contacts will be made that will feed into this deliverable as part of Task 6.1.

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